

Assessing the Sustainable Drinking Water Management Strategies on Dhaka Division in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT: In areas like Dhaka division of Bangladesh, particularly five districts of outside Dhaka mega city (Narayanganj, Narsingdi, Gazipur, Gopalganj) where access to safe drinking water may be limited, efforts often focus on improving infrastructure to provide clean water sources, implementing water purification technologies, promoting hygiene and sanitation practices, and enforcing regulations to ensure water quality standards are met. The management of pure drinking water consumption typically involves a multifaceted approach encompassing infrastructure development, water treatment, distribution systems, public health education, and regulatory measures. Community engagement and partnerships with local authorities, NGOs, and international organizations also play a crucial role in addressing water-related challenges and ensuring sustainable access to clean drinking water. This study investigates Pure Drinking Water Consumption Management practices in the five districts of Dhaka division, focusing on both domestic and industrial sectors. Through a combination of surveys, interviews, and data analysis, key factors influencing water usage patterns are identified. The research examines the impact of population growth, urbanization, climate change, and infrastructure development on water demand. Additionally, it evaluates existing water management policies and initiatives, highlighting their effectiveness and areas for improvement. The finding results aim to provide insights for policymakers, urban planners, and local communities, to develop sustainable water management strategies in Dhaka division in Bangladesh. This study focus on collected on primary data from the different people on five districts of Dhaka division (Dhaka, Narayanganj, Narsingdi, Gazipur, Gopalganj) in Bangladesh. Access to clean drinking water reduces the incidence of water borne diseases such as cholera, diarrhea, and typhoid, leading to improved public health and reduced healthcare costs. Reliable access to safe drinking water contributes to better hygiene practices, increased productivity, and improved overall quality of life for residents, particularly women and children who often bear the burden of water collection and household chores. Engaging local communities in water management initiatives fosters a sense of ownership, empowerment, and collective responsibility for safeguarding water resources and promoting sustainable practices.

KEYWORDS: Drinking Water, Sustainable Management, Responsibility, People.

INTRODUCTION

Dhaka division situated in the central region of Bangladesh faces significant challenges in water consumption management. Access to clean and reliable water sources, as well as efficient management of water resources, is crucial for sustaining livelihoods and ensuring the well-being of its residents. Recognizing these challenges, this study aims to comprehensively assess the current scenario of water consumption and management practices on five districts of Dhaka division (Dhaka, Narayanganj, Narsingdi, Gazipur, Gopalganj). Community well-being: understanding water consumption patterns and challenges is pivotal in enhancing the health and well-being of Dhaka residents. The findings of this survey will provide essential data for local authorities and policymakers to formulate strategies aimed at improving water supply infrastructure and management practices.

Pure drinking water is essential for human health and well-being. While many parts of the world have access to clean water, there are still regions where clean water is scarce or contaminated. Efforts to improve access to clean water, such as water purification systems and infrastructure development, are crucial for ensuring everyone has access to safe drinking water. Access to clean drinking water varies across Asia. Some countries have well-developed infrastructure and water treatment facilities, providing safe drinking water to the majority of their populations. However, in other parts of Asia, especially in rural areas and informal settlements, access to clean water remains a challenge due to insufficient infrastructure, pollution, and inadequate sanitation practices. Efforts to improve access to clean water in these regions often involve investment in infrastructure, technology, and education on water hygiene and conservation.

Bangladesh faces significant challenges regarding access to pure drinking water. While efforts have been made to improve access, contamination from arsenic and microbial pathogens remains a concern in many areas. The government, along with NGOs and

international organizations, has been working to address these issues through initiatives such as installing arsenic removal filters and improving sanitation infrastructure. Despite progress, ensuring universal access to pure drinking water continues to be a priority for Bangladesh. Managing clean drinking water consumption globally involves a multifaceted approach including conservation efforts, infrastructure development, water treatment technologies, and policy interventions. It requires collaboration between governments, NGOs, and communities to ensure equitable access and sustainable use of water resources. Efforts include promoting water-saving practices, investing in efficient irrigation systems, protecting watersheds, and implementing policies to prevent pollution and ensure safe drinking water for all.

In Asia, managing clean drinking water consumption is crucial due to the region's diverse water challenges, including rapid urbanization, industrialization, and population growth. Efforts focus on improving infrastructure, such as expanding access to piped water and sanitation systems, especially in rural areas. Conservation measures like rainwater harvesting and wastewater recycling are also promoted. Additionally, there's an emphasis on addressing pollution from industrial and agricultural sources, as well as promoting community involvement and awareness to ensure sustainable water management practices. International cooperation and technology transfer play key roles in addressing water scarcity and ensuring access to clean drinking water across Asia.

1. Background of the Study:

Bangladesh, managing clean drinking water consumption is a critical issue due to challenges such as arsenic contamination in groundwater and access to safe water in rural areas. Efforts include implementing water purification technologies, such as arsenic removal filters, and promoting the use of surface water sources where possible. Community-based initiatives, like the installation of hand pumps and tube wells, aim to improve access to clean water in remote areas. Government programs also focus on raising awareness about waterborne diseases and promoting hygiene practices to ensure safe drinking water consumption. Additionally, international partnerships and aid support initiatives to address water quality and accessibility issues in Bangladesh.

Effective management of pure drinking water consumption is paramount for ensuring public health and sustainable resource use. It involves a multi-faceted approach that encompasses both conservation and distribution strategies. Conservation efforts, such as promoting water-efficient appliances and behaviors, are essential for reducing wastage. Additionally, investing in infrastructure to improve water treatment and distribution systems can enhance access to clean water. Education plays a crucial role in raising awareness about the importance of clean water and fostering responsible consumption habits. Furthermore, implementing policies to regulate water usage and prevent pollution is vital for safeguarding water quality. By prioritizing efficient management practices and fostering collaboration between stakeholders, we can ensure equitable access to pure drinking water while preserving this precious resource for future generations.

Analyzing the purity of drinking water is crucial for safeguarding public health. This process involves rigorous testing for various contaminants, including bacteria, heavy metals, pesticides, and chemicals. Advanced laboratory techniques, such as chromatography and spectrometry, are employed to detect even trace amounts of pollutants. Additionally, microbial testing ensures the absence of harmful pathogens. Regular monitoring and analysis of drinking water sources, treatment facilities, and distribution systems are essential for identifying potential risks and ensuring compliance with safety standards. By conducting comprehensive analyses and promptly addressing any issues identified, authorities can maintain the integrity of drinking water supplies and protect the well-being of communities. Pure drinking water is essential for human health and well-being. While many parts of the world have access to clean water, there are still regions where clean water is scarce or contaminated. Efforts to improve access to clean water, such as water purification systems and infrastructure development, are crucial for ensuring everyone has access to safe drinking water.

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Additionally, microbial testing ensures the absence of harmful pathogens. Regular monitoring and analysis of drinking water sources, treatment facilities, and distribution systems are essential for identifying potential risks and ensuring compliance with safety standards. By conducting comprehensive analyses and promptly addressing any issues identified, authorities can maintain the integrity of drinking water supplies and protect the well-being of communities.

Managing pure drinking water involves a comprehensive approach that encompasses various aspects, from sourcing and treatment

to distribution and consumption. Pure drinking water typically originates from natural sources such as rivers, lakes, groundwater, or reservoirs. It's essential to assess the quality of these sources regularly to ensure they meet safety standards. Monitoring factors like contamination from industrial waste, agricultural runoff, or naturally occurring pollutants is crucial. Water treatment plants play a critical role in purifying water for consumption. Processes like sedimentation, filtration, and disinfection (often using chlorine or UV light) remove impurities, pathogens, and contaminants. Advanced treatment methods may also be employed to address specific pollutants like heavy metals or organic compounds. Efficient distribution systems are necessary to transport treated water from treatment plants to consumers' taps. Infrastructure maintenance, regular inspections, and leak detection are essential to prevent contamination and ensure water quality throughout the distribution network.

Educating the public about the importance of pure drinking water and proper water management practices is vital. This includes promoting water conservation, encouraging the use of water-efficient appliances, and raising awareness about potential contaminants and health risks. Advancements in technology play a significant role in improving water management. From innovative filtration systems to real-time monitoring devices, technology can enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of water treatment and distribution processes. Sustainable water management practices aim to balance water use with environmental conservation and long-term resource availability. This includes initiatives like rainwater harvesting, wastewater recycling, and ecosystem preservation to ensure the continued availability of clean drinking water for future generations. Analyzing the purity of drinking water is crucial for safeguarding public health.

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Educating the public about the importance of pure drinking water and proper water management practices is vital. This includes promoting water conservation, encouraging the use of water-efficient appliances, and raising awareness about potential contaminants and health risks. Advancements in technology play a significant role in improving water management. From innovative filtration systems to real-time monitoring devices, technology can enhance the efficiency and effectiveness of water treatment and distribution processes. Sustainable water management practices aim to balance water use with environmental conservation and long-term resource availability. This includes initiatives like rainwater harvesting, wastewater recycling, and ecosystem preservation to ensure the continued availability of clean drinking water for future generations.

1.2 Rational of the Study:

Water Scarcity Concerns: The district encounters periodic challenges related to water scarcity, with interruptions in the supply of potable water affecting households and communities.

Quality of Drinking Water: Reports of waterborne illnesses and dissatisfaction with the quality of drinking water highlight the necessity for improved management and quality assurance measures.

Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): This survey aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 6, which emphasizes ensuring access to clean water and sanitation for all.

1.3 Research Questions:

1. What are the primary sources of drinking water in households across different areas of five districts of Dhaka division (Dhaka, Narayanganj, Narsingdi, Gazipur, Gopalgan)?
2. How does the reliability of water supply vary among different regions within Dhaka division?
3. What are the prevalent water consumption patterns in households, and how do they differ based on socio-economic factors?
4. What measures do households undertake to treat drinking water, and what factors influence these choices?

1.4 Objectives of the Study:

Some objectives on water consumption management in Dhaka division in Bangladesh:

1. To determine the prevailing water consumption patterns in households and the primary sources of drinking water on Dhaka division in Bangladesh.
2. To understand the frequency and nature of interruption in water supply experienced by residents on Dhaka division in Bangladesh.
3. To gauge residents' satisfaction with the quality of their drinking water and assess whether waterborne illnesses are

linked to water quality.

4. To identify the measures taken by residents to conserve water in their households and evaluate the awareness of water conservation practices.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

We referred several research papers on Physico-chemical and microbial analysis of ground water as well as surface water of two polder. Different physico-chemical parameters are compared with WHO standards to determine the quality of water suitable or not suitable for drinking purpose.

Yadav (2010), Rasayan, carried out experimental work on physico-chemical properties of ground water taken from four blocks (Suar, Milak, Bilaspur, Shahabad) of Rampur district, Uttar Pradesh, India from each block fifteen villages are under studied. It has been found that physico-chemical parameters of water indicate considerable variation. Most of ground water samples do not comply with WHO standards for drinking purpose only eight locations shows quality of ground water suitable for drinking water.

Rajesh Kumar (2011), Carried out correlation analysis of ground water quality in and around Shahzad Nagar block of district, Uttar Pradesh, India. For present investigation, ground water samples from twenty five locations are selected and analysis of water was carried out using standard methods. Chemical parameters compared with WHO, USPH, European and ICMR Standards shows considerable variation.

The statistical analysis showed that E.C. has positive and significant correlation with TDS, TH, Ca²⁺, Na⁺, SO₄²⁻, Mg²⁺, and TA (Makwana, 2012). Carried out work on drinking water collected from fifteen sampling stations of water (bore well, wells and lacks) of Gandhinagar territory area to determine water quality index, physico-chemical analysis shows that parameters of drinking water shows the variation from prescribed value.

Shah (2012), report about quality of drinking water samples of kathalal territory, Gujarat from twenty different locations bore wells water samples are collected for physico-chemical analysis. Studies shows that on an average most of water samples in this area were suitable for drinking purpose and a very simple pre-treatment also enough to make the water potable.

Regli and co-workers (1991) and Hot and co-workers (2003) have showed that the prevalence of viruses in water may differ from that of indicator organisms. Low numbers of viruses are present in water samples compared to indicator organisms, viruses are only excreted for short periods of time while coliform bacteria is excreted continuously, and the structure, size, composition and morphological differences between viruses and bacteria also had an influence on behavioral and survival patterns of these microorganisms

(Regli et al., 1991; Hot et al., 2003).2012, carried out work on assessment of ground water in koilwar block of Bhojpur (Bihar) to determine water quality index ground water samples from ten different villages were collected. Chemical parameters such of Temp, pH, TH, Cl⁻, F⁻, TDS, Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺, SO₄²⁻ and alkalinity were analyze. The WQI for these samples ranges from 40.67 – 69.59, study show that ground water of koilwar block required treatment before to use, also need protection from contamination.

Usha (2013), carried out work on to determine water quality index and fitness of urban water bodies in Bilari town of Moradabad (Uttar Pradesh). Ground water samples in three different months January, June and September 2011 were collected from ten different sites. Analysis of ground water samples were carried out for different physico-chemical parameters. WQI shows that contamination of water increases day by day. So require treatment for purification before to use.

Neerja Kalra (2012), carried out work on to determine ground water quality from five blocks (Udwantnagar, Taratu, Chapokhar, Piro, Sahar) of Southern, Bhojpur (Bihar) for that purpose then ground water samples were collected from each block, physico-chemical analysis of different parameters compared with ICMR standards for drinking purpose shows that ground water indicate considerable variation, most of ground water samples do not comply with ICMR standards of drinking purpose, few location from study area shows ground water suitable for drinking purpose.

Aher Binano Frontier work was carried out to study physico-chemical parameters of water sample collected from tube well of selected villages in Kalwan Tahsil of Nasik district for present investigation. Water samples were collected randomly from five different stations. Result shows that physico-chemical parameters of collected water samples are within permissible limit in study area so water is suitable for irrigation and drinking purpose. Adhena Ayaliwe Werkneh (2015), carried out work on physico-chemical analysis of drinking water quality at Jigjiga city, Ethiopia. For present investigation of tap water samples shows that potable water is safe enough to be consumed by humans.

K. Elangovan (2010) carried out characteristics of tube well water for district Erode (India) states that ground water quality of 60 locations in Erode district during pre- monsoon and postmonsoon seasons. Ground water samples were tested for 11 physico-chemical parameters following the standard methods and procedures. World Health Organization (WHO) standards were adopted for calculation of water quality index (WQI) by using the methods proposed by Horton and modified by Tiwari and Mishra.

Saxena et al. (2008) carried out a study on Chambal River in Madhya Pradesh. The objective was to study physico-chemical parameters from the water samples drawn. they studied DO, Turbidity, pH, electrical conductivity etc. other parameters like total

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hardness, chloride, nitrates, sulphates, BOD, COD, Na and K were also studied.

Ugwn et al. (2012) 14 analyzed the impact of growing population in the city of Abuja in Nigeria by studying the seasonal chemical characteristic of the usma river. The study revealed that all parameters measured were within the permissible level except total suspended solid which exceeded for all seasons.

TDS in water are inorganic salts and small amounts of organic matter, total dissolved solid in water may be originated from natural sources sewage effluent discharges urban runoff to and industrial discharges TDS is linked to taste WHO recommended 1000 mg/l TDS as guideline values. Ground water quality of various different has been studied in tube well, Bore well and open well, by a number of researchers. A few of them has been listed.

LeChevallier and co-workers (1996) have showed that improper filtration, temperature, inadequate disinfection and treatment procedures, biofilms and high assimilable organic carbon (AOC) levels, could all be responsible for the regrowth of coliform bacteria in water samples.

(Rice et al., 1990) Globally *E. coli* is used as the preferred indicator of faecal pollution (Edberg et al., 2000). It is a Gram negative bacterium and predominantly an inhabitant of the intestines of warm blooded animals and humans, which is used to indicate recent faecal pollution of water samples; Rice et al., 1991; WHO, 1996a; Edberg et al., 2000). Confirmation tests for *E. coli* include testing for the presence of the enzyme β -glucuronidase, Gram staining, absence of urease activity, production of acid and gas from lactose and indole production (Mac Faddin, 1980; Rice et al., 1991; Standard Methods, 1995).

Gupta et al. (1994) studied the quality of drinking water in the Birbnu district of west Bengal and found high concentration of manganese, Fe and Zinc. He has shown the quality assessment of well water in the rural area around Rewa. Kumarswamy et al. (1997). Analyzed the ground water coastal basin in visakhapatnam and found that the chemical quality of the water has been effected by domestic waste water and sea water.

Gupta et al. (1999) 22 have found high hardness value and MPN of coli form in the drinking water of satna, Madhyapradesh. Dahiya et al.(1999) has studied the physico-chemical characteristics of groundwater in rural areas of Thosham sub-division Bhivani district Hariyana.

Shreenivas et al. (2000) studied the ground water quality of Hyderabad by taking 32 tube well water samples and reported the electrical conductivity. Total dissolved solids, total alkalinity, hardness, calcium, magnesium, sodium and chlorides were above the permissible limit according to WHO and Indian standards.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY:

3.1 Introduction

The basic aim of the chapter is to elucidate the methodology that has been adopted for the study and its rationality for selecting those approaches. This chapter not only describes the methodology, but also depicts the quality assessment of the research by bringing reliability and validity test. The study of water consumption management on Dhaka division in Bangladesh was essentially involving collection of data. The methodology includes the ways in which data has been collected, the techniques which are used for analyses, and the theoretical foundation and empirical design of the model.

3.2 The Study Area

Define the specific geographic region within on Dhaka division (Dhaka, Narayanganj, Narsingdi, Gazipur, Gopalganj) in Bangladesh where the study will focus. This might include not particular districts, municipalities, or even specific neighborhoods. Identify the primary water sources in the area, such as rivers, lakes, reservoirs, groundwater, or piped water supply systems, which could form the basis of your study. Understand the population distribution, density, and demographic characteristics within the chosen area, as these factors can significantly influence water consumption patterns. Assess the existing water infrastructure, including treatment plants, distribution networks, storage facilities, and any challenges or deficiencies in these. Consider socio-economic aspects such as income levels, employment patterns, education, and access to water-related services that might impact water usage practices. Identify any environmental issues affecting water resources, like pollution, climate-related changes, or ecosystem health within the study area.

Table 3.1: Ten villages/areas under five Upozila and five Districts of Dhaka Division in Bangladesh.

Division	Districts	Upozila/Thana	Village/Area	Respondents
Dhaka Division	Dhaka	Jatrabari	Dholaipar,	20
			Kadamtali	20
	Narayanganj	Araihazar	Gahardi,	20
			Gopaldi	20
	Narsingdi	Madhobdi	Khadimarchor,	20
			Puranchor	20

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	Gazipur	Kaliakair	Fulbaria	20
			Chapair	20
	Gopalganj	Gopalganj Sadar	Ghobra,	20
			Sonakur	20
Total Respondents				200

3.3 Selection of sample and sampling procedure

In the selection of sampling method is used for data collection and this need an organized questionnaire. A well-structured has been prepared for the research questions and for the accuracy of the results at the first launched pilot survey on 20 respondents and then prepared a final questionnaire to the data with high care. Considering accessibility and availability of sample local respondent a total of 200 respondents were chosen randomly for the survey.

3.4 Period of Data Collection

This research study is mainly based on primary data. Primary data has been collected from the selected sample from several types of residence on ten villages under five Upozila and five districts (Dhaka, Narayanganj, Gazipur, Narsingdi, Gopalganj) from January to June 2025 using a prepared structured questionnaire.

3.5 Analytical Techniques

The filled-in interview schedules were scrutinized and the collected data were processed and edited first. Then the collected data were shifted to excel worksheets where these data were compelled, classified, tabulated and graphed. A number of tables and graphed were prepared keeping in view the aims and objectives of the study. Mainly the two types of techniques of analysis were used in this study. These are:

3.5.1 Tabulation Technique:

Tabulation technique is well known and widely used technique. Tabulation technique is the technique that is commonly followed to find out the crude association or difference between variables. In this study, tabulation technique was followed to illustrate the whole picture of analysis. The tabulation analysis was mainly based on averages, percentages, frequencies of respondents based on primary data on January to June 2025.

3.5.2 Graphical Analysis:

Graphical analysis was carried out to focus on the factors that influence the level of socioeconomic impact on local people on the ten villages/areas under five Upozila and five districts (Dhaka, Narayanganj, Gazipur, Narsingdi, Gopalganj). Upon collected primary data on based on January to June 2025 plotted tabulation and using these tables' draw and analysis different types of graphs like pie-chart, bar graph, line graph etc.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

This chapter is result and summary discussion of the finding and other issues associated with this study. The result and discussion are associated with two aspects; the first one is tabular presentation of data and the second one is graphical presentation of them. Various data related with the study is calculated containing frequency, cumulative total of frequency and their respective percentage. After that, tabulated value is shown graphically building relation with respective variables.

Table 4.1: Age Distribution of the Respondents (Based on field survey 2025)

Age	No of Frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
25-30	80	80	40%
30-35	60	140	30%
35-40	24	164	12%
Above 40	36	200	18%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

From the table 4.1 indicates that the age distribution contains 40% respondents age 25-30 years, 30% respondents age 30-35 years, 12% respondents age 35-40 years and 18% respondents age above 40 years. The highest Respondents are young generation 25-30 ages and lowest respondents are 35 to 40 age groups.

Figure 4.1: Graphical presentation of the Age Distribution

From the above pie chart it shows that the age distribution contains 40% respondents age 25- 30 years, 30% respondents age 30-35 years, 12% respondents age 35-40 years and 18% respondents age above 40 years.

Table 4. 2: Distribution of Occupation (Based on field survey 2025)

Occupation	No of Frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
Agriculture	80	80	40%
Business	24	104	12%
Job	32	136	16%
Entrepreneur	40	168	20%
Others	20	200	10%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above table shows the respondents profile of Occupation. The main occupation is agriculture whereas 80 frequencies represent 40% and the same frequency indicates job, entrepreneur and others, those all are represents 16% occupations. More less is Business is 24 frequencies and it is shows 12% only and highest occupation is agriculture sector.

Figure 4.2: Distribution of Occupation.

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The above column chart shows that 40% respondents are in agriculture, 12% respondents are in business sector, 16% respondents are in job, 12% respondents are in entrepreneur and 20% respondents are in others sector.

Table 4.3: Use of fuel for cooking (Based on field survey 2025)

Use of fuel distribution	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
Wood	88	88	44%
Gas	52	140	26%
Electricity	20	160	10%
Animal dung	40	200	20%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

Table 4.3 shows the use of fuel for cooking. There is highest use of wood 44% and lowest use electricity only 10% for cooking. Another 26% use gas and 20% use animal dung for cooking.

Figure 4.3: Use of fuel for cooking.

The above figure reveals that 44% of the respondents use Wood, 28% of the respondents use Gas, 10% of the respondents use Electricity and 20% of the respondents use Animal dung.

Table 4.4: Water Supply Process (Based on field survey 2025)

Name of Water Supply Process	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
Public Tap	40	40	20%
Private Well	104	144	52%
Rainwater Harvesting	24	168	12%
Others	32	200	16%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above table shows the Water Supply Process. The chart shows that 20% respondents use in Public Tap. Highest 52% respondents are in Private Well and lowest 12% respondents are used in Rainwater Harvesting, and 16% respondents are in others sector.

Graphical presentation about water Supply Process is shown below:

Figure 4.4: Water Supply Process

The above line chart shows that the name of Water Supply Process. The chart shows that 20% respondents are in Public Tap, 52% respondents are in Private Well, 12% respondents are in Rainwater Harvesting, and 16% respondents are in others sector.

Table 4.5: Water Supply Quantity and Quality (Based on field survey 2025)

Opinion	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
Very Satisfied	28	28	14%
Satisfied	48	76	24%
Neutral	80	156	40%
Dissatisfied	24	180	12%
Very Dissatisfied	20	200	10%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above schedule shows that Water Supply Quantity and Quality. The chart shows that the opinion of people where 14% respondents are in Very Satisfied, 24% respondents are in highest Satisfied, 40% respondents are in Neutral, less 12% respondents are in Dissatisfied and more less 10% respondents are in Very Dissatisfied.

Graphical presentation about Water Supply Quantity and Quality is shown below:

Figure 4.5: Water Supply Quantity and Quality

The above column chart shows that Water Supply Quantity and Quality. The chart shows that the opinion of people where 14% respondents are in Very Satisfied, 24% respondents are in Satisfied, 40% respondents are in Neutral, 12% respondents are in Dissatisfied and 10% respondents are in Very Dissatisfied.

Table 4.6: Water Access per Day (Based on field survey 2025)

Time Period	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage(%)
Less than 4 hours	60	60	30%
4-8 hours	72	132	36%
8-12 hours	44	176	22%
More than 12 hours	24	200	12%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above table shows that Water Access per Day. The table shows that 30% respondents are in less than 4 hours and 36% respondents are in 4-8 hours, 22% respondents are in 8-12 hours and lowest 12% respondents are in more than 12 hours. Graphical presentation about Water Access per Day is shown below.

Figure 4.6: Water Access per Day

The above bar graph shows that Water Access per Day. The table shows that 30% respondents are in less than 4 hours and 36% respondents are in 4-8 hours, 22% respondents are in 8-12 hours and lowest 12% respondents are in more than 12 hours.

Table 4.7: The Cost of Water Services (Based on field survey 2025)

Cost of Water Services	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage(%)
Very Affordable	24	24	12%
Affordable	40	64	20%
Neutral	60	124	30%

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Expensive	52	176	26%
Very Expensive	24	200	12%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above column chart shows that The Cost of Water Services. The chart shows that 12% respondents are in Very Affordable, 20% respondents are in Affordable, the highest 30% respondents are in Neutral, 26% respondents are in Expensive and less 12% respondents are in Very Expensive.

Graphical presentation about The Cost of Water Services is shown below:

Figure 4.7: The Cost of Water Services

The above column chart shows that The Cost of Water Services. The chart shows that 12% respondents are in Very Affordable, 20% respondents are in Affordable, 30% respondents are in Neutral, 26% respondents are in Expensive and 12% respondents are in Very Expensive.

Table 4.8: The Safely of Water Supply (Based on field survey 2025)

Opinion	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
Very Satisfied	24	24	12%
Satisfied	60	84	30%
Neutral	80	168	40%
Dissatisfied	28	192	14%
Very Dissatisfied	08	200	4%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above table 4.8 shows that the opinion of people for the safely of Water Supply is 12% of the respondents very satisfied, 30% of the respondents are satisfied, highest 40% of the respondents are neutral, 14% of the respondents are the Dissatisfied and less 4% of the respondents are Neutral. The pie chart shows the highest percentage is satisfied and the lowest part is Very Dissatisfied. Graphical presentation of The Safely of Water Supply is shown below:

Figure 4.8: The Safety of Water Supply

The above pie chart shows that the opinion of people for the safety of Water Supply is 12% of the respondents very satisfied, 30% of the respondents are satisfied, 40% of the respondents are neutral, 14% of the respondents are the Dissatisfied and 4% of the respondents are Neutral. The pie chart shows the highest percentage is satisfied and the lowest part is Very Dissatisfied

Table 4.9: Educational Programs on Water Conservation (Based on field survey 2025)

Opinion	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
Strongly Agree	72	72	36%
Agree	80	152	40%
Neutral	24	176	12%
Disagree	16	192	8%
Strongly Disagree	08	200	4%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above table 4.9 shows that the Educational Programs on Water Conservation is 36% of the respondents strongly agree, 40% of the respondents are agree, 12% of the respondents are neutral, 8% of the respondents are the Disagree and less only 4% of the respondents are strongly disagree. The table shows the highest percentage is agreed and the lowest part is strongly disagreed

Graphical presentation about Educational Programs is shown below:

Figure 4.9: Educational Programs on Water Conservation

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The above bar chart 4.9 shows that the **Educational Programs on Water Conservation** is 36% of the respondents strongly agree, 40% of the respondents are agree, 12% of the respondents are neutral, 8% of the respondents are the Disagree and less only 4% of the respondents are strongly disagree. The bar graph shows the highest percentage is agreed and the lowest part is strongly disagreeing.

Table 4.10: Knowledge about Water Conservation and Sustainable (Based on field survey 2025)

Opinion	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
Very Knowledge	24	24	12%
Knowledge	80	104	40%
Neutral	88	192	44%
Not very Knowledge	08	200	4%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above table 4.10 shows that the **Knowledge about Water Conservation and Sustainable** is 12% of the respondents very knowledgeable, 40% of the respondents are Knowledge, highest 44% of the respondents are neutral, 8% of the respondents are the Disagree and less only 4% of the respondents are Not very Knowledge.

Graphical presentation about Water Conservation and Sustainable is shown below:

Figure 4.10: Knowledge about Water Conservation and Sustainable

The above graph shows that the **Knowledge about Water Conservation and Sustainable** is 12% of the respondents very knowledgeable, 40% of the respondents are Knowledge, highest 44% of the respondents are neutral, 8% of the respondents are the Disagree and less only 4% of the respondents is not very Knowledge. The highest percentage is Neutral and lowest percentage is not very knowledge.

Table 4.11: Water Services Provider (Based on field survey 2025)

Opinion	No of frequency	Cumulative	Percentage (%)
Very Satisfied	16	16	8%
Satisfied	80	96	40%
Neutral	76	172	38%
Dissatisfied	16	188	8%
Very Dissatisfied	12	200	6%
Total	200		100%

(Author calculation based on collected data)

The above table 4.11 shows that the opinion of people for the **water services provider** is 8% of the respondents very satisfied, more 40% of the respondents are satisfied, 38% of the respondents are neutral, 8% of the respondents are the Dissatisfied and lowest 6% of the respondents are Very Dissatisfied. The pie chart shows the highest percentage is satisfied and the lowest part is Very Dissatisfied.

Graphical presentation of Water Services Provider

The above pie chart shows that the opinion of people for the water services provider is 8% of the respondents very satisfied, 40% of the respondents are satisfied, 38% of the respondents are neutral, 8% of the respondents are the Dissatisfied and 6% of the respondents are Very Dissatisfied. The pie chart shows the highest percentage is satisfied and the lowest part is Very Dissatisfied.

5. POLICY RECOMMENDATION

Effective water consumption management is essential for ensuring access to clean and safe drinking water, promoting public health, and safeguarding the environment. In Dhaka division, like many other regions, sustainable water management practices are crucial to address challenges such as water scarcity, pollution, and inadequate infrastructure.

1. Develop a comprehensive plan to upgrade and expand water treatment, distribution, and storage infrastructure to ensure reliable access to clean water for all residents.
2. Implement policies to promote water conservation practices such as rainwater harvesting, efficient irrigation techniques, and public awareness campaigns to reduce wastage.
3. Encourage active participation of local communities in water management decision-making processes through public consultations, community forums, and partnerships with local organizations.
4. Establish and enforce regulations to prevent water pollution and contamination, including monitoring industrial discharges, regulating agricultural runoff, and enforcing sanitation standards.
5. Integrate technology such as remote sensing, GIS mapping, and data analytics to improve monitoring, forecasting, and management of water resources.
6. Provide training and capacity-building programs for government officials, water management professionals, and community members to enhance skills and knowledge in sustainable water management practices.
7. Consider implementing water pricing mechanisms that reflect the true cost of water provision and encourage conservation while ensuring affordability for low-income households.
8. Foster collaboration between government agencies, NGOs, private sector stakeholders, and academia to coordinate efforts and leverage resources for effective water management.

6. CONCLUSION

This conclusion with policy recommendations aimed at improving water consumption management in Dhaka region, focusing on infrastructure development, conservation measures, community engagement, and regulatory frameworks. By implementing these policies, Dhaka can enhance its water resilience, ensure equitable access to clean water for all residents, and protect its water resources for future generations. Effective water consumption management in Dhaka division (Dhaka, Narayanganj, Narsingdi, Gazipure and Gopalganj) requires a multifaceted approach that addresses infrastructure development, conservation practices, community engagement, and technological innovation. By investing in resilient infrastructure, promoting water conservation measures, engaging local communities in decision-making processes, and leveraging technology for efficient resource management, sustainable improvement can be achieved. With concerted efforts and collaboration among stakeholders, Dhaka region can move towards a more resilient and equitable water management system that meets the needs of its residents while safeguarding water resources for future generation. The management of pure drinking water consumption in five districts of Dhaka division (Dhaka, Narayanganj, Narsingdi, Gazipur and Gopalganj) of Bangladesh is a critical endeavor with significant

implications for public health, socioeconomic development, and environmental sustainability. Through a comprehensive approach encompassing infrastructure development, water treatment, distribution systems, public health education, regulatory measures, community engagement, and partnerships. This study area can achieve tangible results such as improved health outcomes, enhanced quality of life, community empowerment, economic development, environmental sustainability, and resilience to climate change. By prioritizing access to safe and clean drinking water and implementing effective management practices, Dhaka division of Bangladesh can create a healthier, more prosperous, and sustainable future for its residents.

REFERENCES

- 1) "Asian Development Bank Dhaka Water Services Survey Final Report". Consultant: Khondaker Azharul Haq, October, 2005.
- 2) Abu M, Kamal U, Rob K (2003): Delineation of the coastal zone Dhaka, PDO-ICZMP, Bangladesh.
- 3) Aghazadeh N, Chitsazan M, Golestan Y (2017): Hydrochemistry and quality assessment of groundwater in the Ardabil area, Iran. *Applied Water Science*, 7(7): 3599-3616.
- 4) Ahmad H (2019): Bangladesh coastal zone management status and future trends. *Journal of Coastal Zone Management*, 22(1): 466.
- 5) Ahmed N, Bodrud-Doza et al. (2019): Hydrogeochemical evaluation and statistical analysis of groundwater of Sylhet, north-eastern Bangladesh. *Acta Geochim*, 38: 440–455. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11631018-0303-6>.
- 6) APHA (2005): American Public Health Association. Standard methods for the examination of water and wastewater. APHA Washington DC, USA.
- 7) Bahar MM, Reza MS (2010): Hydrochemical characteristics and quality assessment of shallow groundwater in a coastal area of Southwest Bangladesh. *Environmental Earth Science*, 61: 1065–1073. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12665009-0427-4>. B.
- 8) Gupta, H. V., and Sorooshian, S. (1996). "Automatic calibration of conceptual rainfall-runoff models: Sensitivity to calibration data." *J. Hydro.*, 181, 23 – 48.
- 9) Kahlowan M. A., Tahir M. A., H. Rasheed and K. P. Bhatti, (2006): Water Quality Status, National Water Quality Monitoring Programme, Fourth Technical Report. Pakistan Council of Research in water Resources.
- 10) S. Dahiya, D. Datta, H.S. Kushwaha, A fuzzy synthetic evaluation approach for assessment of chemical quality of groundwater for drinking purposes, *Environ. Geol.* 8 (2005) 158–165.
- 11) S. Dahiya, A. Kaur, Assessment of physico-chemical characteristic of underground water in rural areas of Tosham subdivision, Bhiwani-Haryana, *J. Environ. Pollut.* 6 (1999) 281–288.
- 12) N. Kalra's 4 research works with 35 citations, including: Hydrochemical analysis and evaluation of ground water quality in Sandesh block, Bhojpur (Bihar)
- 13) Rajesh kumar and S.S. yadav (2011) 'Correlation analysis of. Ground water quality in and around Shahzad nagar block of. Rampur District, Uttar Pradesh, India.
- 14) Shaibur MR, Parvin S, Ahmmmed I, Rahaman MH, Das TK, Sarwar S (2021b): Gradients of salinity in water sources of Batiaghata, Dacope and Koyra upazila of coastal Khulna district, Bangladesh. *Environmental Challenge* 4(2021), 100152 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envc.2021.100152>.
- 15) Shaibur MR, Rizvi MM, Islam MK, Shamsunnahar (2019f): Salinity causes ecosystem disruption and biodiversity losses in Beel Khuksia: Keshabpur, Jashore, Bangladesh. *Environmental and Biological Research*, 1(1): 1-11.
- 16) Shaibur MR, Shamim AHM, Khan MH (2019g): Water quality of different sources at Buri Goalini and Gabura unions of Shyamnagar upazila, Bangladesh. *Environmental and Biological Research*, 1(1): 3243.
- 17) Shaibur MR, Shamim AHM, Khan MH, and Tanzia FKS (2017b): Exploration of soil quality in agricultural perspective at Gabura and Buri Goalini union: Shyamnagar, Satkhira, Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Environmental Science*, 32: 89-96.
- 18) Shaibur MR, Tanzia FKS, Karim MM, Rahman MH (2017c): Aspects of Bangladesh water development board on the ecosystems and water quality of Nalamara beel in Narail District of Bangladesh. *Bangladesh Journal of Environmental Science*, 32: 144-151
- 19) Shammi M, Rahman MM, Islam MA, Bodrud-Doza M, Zahid A, Akter Y, Quaiyum S, Kurasaki M (2017): Spatio-temporal assessment and trend analysis of surface water salinity in the coastal region of Bangladesh. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 24(16): 14273-14290.
- 20) Shammi M, Rahman R, Rahman M.M, Moniruzzaman M, Bodrud-Doza M, Karmakar B, Uddin MK (2016): Assessment of salinity hazard in existing water resources for irrigation and potentiality of conjunctive uses: a case report from Gopalganj District, Bangladesh. *Sustainable Water Resources Management*, 2(4): 369-378
- 21) Shah, M., Atta, A., Qureshi, M.I. and Shah, H. (2012) Impact of Socio Economic Status (SES) of Family on the Academic Achievements of Students. *Gomal University Journal of Research*, 28, 12-17.

- 22) Srinivas, G., Kusumary, P., Krishnav, M., et al. (2000) Mutant p53 Protein, BCL-2/ Bax Ratio and Apoptosis in Pediatric Acute Lymphoblastic Leukemia. *Journal of Cancer Research and Clinical Oncology*, 126, 62-67. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s004320050010>
- 23) Usha Rani, 2013, A study of job satisfaction of employee of small and medium industries having human resource department and not having human resource department in Saurashtra region, Saurashtra University.
- 24) Yadav V, et al. (2010) WITHDRAWN: A phosphate transporter from the root endophytic fungus *Piriformospora indica* plays a role in phosphate transport to the host plant. *J Biol Chem* 285(34):26532-44
- 25) W.R. Ott, *Water Quality Indices: A Survey of Indices Used in the United States*, EPA-600/4- 78-005, US Environmental Protection Agency, Wash- ington, DC, 1978, p. 128